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Rurality and Territoriality: Strategies for Access to Agricultural Advice among Farmers in Lom-Et-Djérem Faced Social Change's

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Abstract

Faced with constraints related to access to agricultural advice provided by public and private organizations in rural areas, and given the multiple challenges associated with supporting farmers, some local approaches to accessing agricultural advice are developed by farmers themselves. These strategies, due to the nature of their interactions and relationships, contribute to the construction of the territory in rural areas. Based on survey data, an analytical framework was developed to observe producers' acquisition of knowledge and know-how. This revealed that they can use local or external sources of information, and develop interactions with one or more sources depending on the opportunities they perceive. The analysis revealed five main methods developed by producers to access agricultural advice. A farmer can adopt any of the strategies deployed in rural areas or participate in all of them.

Keywords: access strategies, agricultural advice, rural environment, adaptation

Introduction

Talking about rurality and territoriality in terms of agricultural advice allows us to see how family agropastoral farms (FAF) mobilize the resources of their environment by adapting their practices to successive modulations in the framework of agricultural advice. For a good number of family agropastoral farms, territoriality expresses a feeling of belonging and a way of behaving within their community, but also a feeling of relative exclusion from agricultural or rural development policies. It is then a question of analyzing the strategies constructed by farmers in their geographical area of belonging, in order to access the agricultural information, they need for the proper conduct of their activity.

For Maxime and Cerf (2002), agricultural advisor means providing information, opinions, making recommendations or suggestions to help the farmer make choices and take action; assuming that the information provided, the actions suggested or the actions defined are good for him and appropriate in his context. As Magne et al. (2011) note, it is about providing information on knowledge relating to more or less specific concerns, all with a certain purpose. According to Picheral (2001), access is the material capacity to access the resources or services offered. This reflects the possibility of using service providers, especially depending on the distance/time ratio, the proximity of the service and the financial possibility of having said service. An agricultural advisory system can be considered as the set of functional links that connect actors and institutions of different hierarchical levels, combined with means by approach in order to intervene in the realization of an

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activity with specific missions for each actor (Sedogo, 2017). It should be noted that the agricultural advice implemented varies according to the actors and their objectives. This allows us to observe a diversity of tools and methods, distinct approaches and agent profiles, and various action mechanisms. With the aim of facilitating decision-making and the implementation of the changes they suggest within farms.

Agricultural extension, before being a program, is an organization of men and women who try to apply in the field the instruments of an agricultural and social modernization policy (Bedrani et al., 1993). Although with the evolution of societies what is informal is called to become formal. Agricultural advice as a development instrument is a practice that in rural areas evolves formally and informally through the presence of more or less linked networks. As a result, the modalities of access to agricultural advice interact with human behavior and influence as a social fact as shown by Kilpatrick and Johns (2003). This induces a deployment of diverse strategies according to the opportunities perceived by farmers, and the dynamism of the interactions that emerge in their environment.

Material and Method

This study, which examines sources of access to agricultural advice, aims to analyze the different strategies deployed by rural producers in the Eastern region of Cameroon to acquire agricultural information. The questionnaire was first developed and then tested through a preliminary survey. This allowed for a review of the focus and observation axes in order to better formalize the questionnaire for the field visit. Data were collected in two stages. First, through 135 questionnaires administered to rural agricultural producers in the Lom-et-Djérem department. This was done using simple random sampling with 45 questionnaires per district of Belabo, Diang and Mandjou. Within each district, 15 questionnaires were administered in three separate locations. Second, through 36 interviews using snowball sampling, influenced by interactions with farmers during the questionnaire administration process. Including 12 interviews in the said districts, and 4 interviews in each of the 3 selected localities per district. Following the themes covered by the questionnaire, a grouping of data was carried out according to the study areas and the intervention areas of the formal and informal actors of agricultural advice. This made it possible to highlight the different strategies used by producers and their motivations. This study being qualitative in nature, descriptive statistics such as percentages were produced to describe the data and their interpretation through content analysis.

I - Identity and environment, territoriality agent among farmers in rural areas

The evolution of contemporary rural societies is characterized by several changes. One of the most important is undoubtedly the construction of territory by endogenous populations, specifically farmers. In the past, identity was constructed through social belonging, but today, it is increasingly constructed through territorial belonging (Bailoni, 2012), given that belonging to the territory can define the original social form within which the family farm is embedded. For it is attachment to a localized human community that constitutes the substance of territoriality and through which social dynamics are observable.

The relationship to territory among rural producers is embodied through a sense of identity in the construction of the identity of their activities. Thus, regardless of rural development policies related to agriculture, the territorial approach, through the environmental cohesion of producers, structures their existence (Tchékoté et al., 2018). This shows that within the agricultural community surveyed, the local reference would remain central in their experience. Because, the link between farmers and their environment clearly shows that collective consciousness in rural areas is not simply reduced to attachment to the territory but also to the production of goods and services. This analysis is also similar to the conclusions of Mathieu (2007) on his analyses between the link between farmers to places and to other inhabitants, but which go against the theories of neoclassical economics. However, farmers, by resisting social mobility, must accept certain personal living conditions by gradually adapting to various changes.

Since land is not an extensible asset, regardless of its agro-ecological properties, it plays a significant role in the dynamism observed among agricultural producers; hence these different adaptation strategies. As a result, the notion of territory is important in the experience of rural farmers as a factor in the construction and recognition

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of their identity (Lorenzini, 2011). Moreover, with the selection of rural land by industrial companies or the practice of corporate family farming using external capital (Tchékoté et al. 2018), dynamic family agropastoral farms select and adopt production techniques that build over the course of the interactions they develop in order to avoid the vicious cycle of withdrawal strategies.

In the study sample, nearly 69% of agricultural producers believe that agriculture is one of the best activities offering contact with nature and a certain freedom, especially when it is encouraged and supported by public policies. Furthermore, in agricultural practice, 48% of respondents are motivated in their activity by their attachment to their land, while 42% are motivated by their environment. These results show that rural farmers, despite their living conditions and the challenges they face, have a positive perception of their living environment and their activity. Moreover, one producer surveyed stated: "The promotion of the rural environment through good local development approaches would further promote agriculture as a career of the future for our children in rural areas." This would then involve the interweaving of the logics of social capital (public authorities, local authorities, elites, consultation groups, young people), with those of the local economy. Thus, the development of the agricultural sector through the territorial approach, interwoven with other opportunities composing the said environment, would be an asset for rural development.

This identity construction of farmers in the local environment reflects the territorial dynamics of their social structure in their diverse components. The rural environment as a living environment for them is then a dynamic environment crossed by multiple relationships of inter-knowledge (Vandenbroucke, 2015). Moreover, 82% of farmers surveyed affirm that they can count on the help of neighbors in case of difficulty, colleagues, or those who practice a parallel or related activity to them. For 67% of farmers, it is easy to organize to carry out projects together when the project instigators are people they perceive as a resource. For 71%, a good level of tolerance exists in their local community through the different networks and forms of communication that structure their relationships. Thus, the mechanical solidarity to which organic solidarity is increasingly intertwined, plays a very important role in the relationships between farmers in their environment. It allows us to observe the adaptations of family farming in rural areas, subject to various circumstances regarding the acquisition of agricultural information.

II- Local dynamism and the construction of agricultural information

These are the strategies implemented by farmers to adapt to changes in their environment in order to remain productive. By agricultural information, we mean any practices, technologies, or knowledge disseminated with an advisory approach, capable of improving or optimizing producers' activities.

Farmers do not react in the same way to information, and they do not behave identically in the same situations. Their social status, personal characteristics, perception of information, and the cultural influence that structures their environment influence their behavior. This allows them to act based on what is presented to them, or based on what they perceive as opportunities in a given situation. This is why several strategies are observed in the acquisition of agricultural information.

II-1. The use of formal programs

In analyzing the understanding of structural adaptations or systematic and comprehensive changes in stakeholder logic, solutions or new practices are born from social expectations. This is why, before becoming formalized and institutionalized, extension services were an informal practice implemented by stakeholders to improve the management of their farms (Bedrani et al., 1993).

Social dynamics and development processes have reconfigured the image of agricultural advisory services, which today increasingly present themselves as structured programs implemented by a group of stakeholders. Today, when we talk about agricultural advisory services, we tend to think more of programs implemented by public authorities, private organizations, donors, and certain third parties as a mechanism. Among the agricultural advisory organizations most cited by respondents are PRO-SAPVA, PRODEL, and PCP-ACEFA. SAILD participates in capacity building, monitoring and advice, and financing of farmers' organizations.

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Among the donors, we have the PNDP, which is a program implemented by the Cameroonian government with the help of development partners, whose mission is to improve the living conditions of populations in rural areas and local governance. They are involved in various ways in terms of agricultural advice, like financing producers, they also support them through advisory support.

According to the reasons given by the producers surveyed, some prefer to use such actors because of their experience and their methods based on modern agricultural practices and scientific advances. Others turn to them because of the related services they provide to producers, namely capacity building and project financing. This allows them to acquire new knowledge, gain access to certain skills and know-how, and build new relationships through training, technical, economic, or management advice, administrative capacity building, or infrastructure improvements.

According to the producers surveyed, these programs, in addition to providing them with trained personnel, allow them to master the technical itineraries of farming and improve farm management. They provide easier access to economic information and technical innovation, and organize themselves to improve their access to markets and other factors of production. To implement development projects, improve governance within farmers' organizations (POs) and marketing, through individual or collective investments.

It should be noted that access to such institutions is generally subject to certain conditions and requires the mobilization of a certain number of skills such as curiosity and fluency in one of the official languages. Based solely on reading and writing skills, these requirements favor access for 68% of respondents. However, of the overall sample, nearly 12% of them are actually supported by a formal agricultural advisory service, although not all of the supervised POs know how to read or write.

Given the limited number of farmers with whom these organizations can work due to their limited resources and the methods they deploy, producers must be competitive in their proposals and learn to integrate with the vision of these organizations. What is most remarkable here is the nascent enthusiasm for farmers who can express themselves in one of the official languages, but who cannot read or write. Indeed, nearly 6% of farmers in our sample who are illiterate but speak one of the official languages are willing to pursue literacy training, even though it will be difficult for them.

Since the formalization of agricultural advisory services came after the phenomenon itself, and the programs implemented can only support a minority of agricultural workers, they deploy several other mechanisms to gain access to advisory services, including targeting.

II-2. Targeting strategies

Targeting is a strategy for access to agricultural advice that arises from the modern configuration of the advisory system. Insofar as the opening or influence of a culture through exoticism creates new behaviors, which can in turn react on the environment generating new phenomena (Kendal, 2001). In this sense, the response to a gap felt in a dynamic local environment generates new practices that in turn lead to new behaviors through interactions. By the example of targeting in the face of the phenomenon of increasingly acquired formalization in agricultural advice.

As Kotler (1999) says, you can't talk to everyone at the same time in the same way. It is therefore necessary to choose precise targets and clearly define those that one wants to reach. In this sense, targeting refers to a choice made by a producer on whom he focuses his efforts in order to achieve his objectives based on a set of indicators. It should be noted that the actor is not a coherent whole, but a human being, thus made up of incoherence, contradictory wills, involuntary inertia and resistance (Beuret, 1997).

That is why producers through targeting strategies will express their goals more in terms of possible reactions to perceived opportunities as defined targets towards which to progress. This depends on the context, possible reactions and representations of their environment. It is not a question for the producer to make an optimum choice, the outcome of any prospect being subject only to prediction; but to opt for a choice based on the objectives, resources and constraints he perceives in a given situation. Because, if the actor seems limited, he is not determined, but remains active to try to give meaning to his actions (Rojot, 2003). During the survey, three

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main targeting methods resulting from the construction of the territory were detected among producers namely: the use of peers, retired advisors, and supervised producers.

Peer Consultation

Peer consulting refers to seeking out certain elders, experts, or colleagues identified in the field who can provide support and advice. This is not simply a matter of relying on colleagues who practice the same activity or are related to it, but rather on farmers who, due to their cross-functional nature, can provide considerable input. 46% of farmers surveyed use this practice. This is the case, for example, for subsistence farmers who rely on market gardeners for training or the acquisition of certain skills. At first glance, it is plausible to wonder what connection there could be between market gardening and subsistence farming, even though they are of different natures and practices.

According to the farmers surveyed, gardeners are very inventive both in terms of the advice they receive and the practices they experiment with on their own farms. In addition, the gardeners' wives are generally food crop producers, which brings them closer to the daily subsistence sector. For this, they generally turn to certain well-located market gardeners to obtain certain advice on farm management and practical tips. Both in terms of cultivation techniques and innovations for improving production. Some farmers interviewed also state that the technique of growing beans on corn stalks in the dry season, which is increasingly widespread in rural areas, comes from the gardeners (market gardeners).

Using retired advisors or agronomists

Using retired advisors or agronomists is also one of the targeting strategies that is increasingly common in rural areas. Some retired advisors return to rural areas to establish farms or other businesses and live there. This brings them a little closer to certain farmers. For some, it's an opportunity to closely observe them at work, to ask for their advice without being pressed by time, objectives, or administrative constraints. For others, it's a way to develop their skills in managing certain constraints. They entrust their difficulties to these retired agents so that they can conduct research, mobilize their knowledge, and leverage their social capital to produce an appropriate and sustainable solution. 21% of farmers surveyed use this technique, while 58% would like to have such an opportunity but are unable to do so due to a lack of a retired advisor nearby or in their portfolio of contacts. With this technique, it is no longer a matter of collective advice under contract and with a superficial portfolio. It is instead an individualized, one-off, community-based, and local advice, through which the retired advisor better understands the constraints and expectations of the producer. Thus, they can devote more time to the producer and provide more in-depth information on their real concerns, or build a local and sustainable solution.

This is for example the case of the technique of sowing corn in pockets, abandoned because of its labor constraints, and its harmful effects on the seeds once in the ground. At the instigation of some farmers, this time in the context of organic corn production, retirement advisors researched and demonstrated a new technique of sowing corn in pockets. They even worked with producers during sowing periods in the fields so that they learned this new technique, as 31 of the producers surveyed testify. Although still restrictive, the harmful effects on seed growth have been removed, and the plots on which they manage to apply this technique are really worth it given the production rate claimed by 12 of the farmers mentioned. It should be noted that this research was driven so that farmers can exploit plots of land that are not very fertile, although beneficial for fertile and overexploited land.

Supervision by supervised producers

The third targeting strategy refers to that of producers supervised by advisory services. Unable to receive direct support from advisory organizations, some producers turn directly to those who have access to them in order to access certain knowledge. This is made possible through independent relationships that emerge within the local environment in rural areas. Indeed, some farmers supervised in their activity teach the acquired knowledge

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within their associations or in their direct environment. During a retransmission session, when the supervised farmers cannot directly address the concerns of their colleagues, they note the concern and share it with their advisor so that they can return to their colleague with an answer.

24% of respondents said they use this method; 37% would like to see this measure formalized through advisors who are designated by speculation in rural areas and receive ongoing training to ensure a certain proximity and punctuality in the service offered. 41% would like to participate in this type of interrelationship in the construction of information in order to form an opinion. 31% are resistant to such a practice, and a small number have no opinion on the matter.

Through targeting strategies, producers can turn to "local experts" to obtain the requested information. They can also observe local practices in the field, such as through segmentation.

II-3. Professional presumption

Producers act according to what they consider opportunities to improve their situation, maintaining, and expanding what they perceive as their margin of freedom (Crozier and Friedberg, 1977). This is why rural producers rely on certain professional agents to access the knowledge they need through a process of segmentation. Professional presumption consists of identifying, at best, the service intermediaries linked to their agricultural activity in a more or less homogeneous manner, whose upstream and downstream services are sufficiently related to the purpose of their operation (Kotler, 1999).

Here, the producer must identify input distributors, feed distributors, or veterinary product distributors, depending on the purpose of their agricultural operation, in order to make these the preferred methods for capitalizing on information. Indeed, these individuals are generally very close to producers as providers of inputs to their business. However, access to advice from professional agents is not always easy when the producer turns to them to acquire new knowledge. Above all, these actors are primarily business entities, since they provide their clients with paid primary products and services, and free secondary advice resulting from a prior transaction. Alternatively, secondary services may, depending on their scope, become chargeable due to the lack of a financial transaction prior to the request.

Upon analysis, although considered third parties in the overall mechanisms for accessing advice, these actors increasingly prefigure the outcome of private advice in rural areas. For they are individuals who, to a certain extent, provide producers with advice or training that more or less meets their expectations. Indeed, to easily access certain knowledge, producers turn to phytosanitary pharmacies, pet food store, fertilizer sellers, seed sellers and similar companies. To do this, they either build loyalty with them, or through the consumption of a product or service to facilitate in-depth exchanges. The advantage with them is their stability, their availability in the face of the immediate interest of producers, and punctuality in providing advice when the producer is in their office.

Nearly 63% of producers in our population use this type of agricultural advice, but at different levels of reference. Much more those who have less than three years in agricultural activity. Although some of these intermediaries are also producers. 29% of respondents are resistant to this type of advice. For the latter, the quality of their advice generally stems from the desire to close a deal, and not from the desire to develop a sustainable solution with them based on their needs.

It should be noted that these intermediaries generally lack training in characterizing a constraint and constructing a problem in order to find a solution. They generally refer to the instructions of the manufacturers or distributors of the products they make available to producers, or to the pace of requests to advise their customers.

Regarding authorized agricultural input distributors, their advice is generally based on the products sold in their establishment, and any service provided revolves around them. This limits their advisory services, as their agents are not trained to go beyond the organization's expertise.

II-4. Positioning in the information landscape

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The analyses clearly show that when it comes to positioning strategies within the information landscape, producers with higher education levels and others are the most adept than others. This is due to their ability to penetrate various information and communication technology (ICT) tools. This is especially true given that, within the sample, they are truly the most interested in newspapers, the internet, and scientific journals.

In rural areas, producers have diverse profiles, reflecting several stratifications of human development that can impact their choices, decisions, perceptions, and even their logic. Since agricultural advisory services are a tool for accessing new knowledge and building knowledge, they are an art that must be forged, and mastering their challenges is an acquired added value. This is why farmers facing advice must make efforts to consolidate and capitalize on their knowledge, because "education is the most powerful weapon for changing the world" (Mandela, 2007).

Positioning within the information spectrum allows producers to adopt strategic behavior in order to determine how they will optimally benefit from all the potential sources of advice they perceive (Kotler, 1999). Indeed, using this method, producers consult a wide range of sources when familiarizing themselves with change. They can learn from individuals, groups, or networks, through local or external sources, which may include training, media, and observation (Faure and Kleene 2004). These sources are generally combined with personal lessons from other farmers, experts, or agricultural associations and organizations.

The distinctive feature of this category is the use of media to access information that is useful to them. This allows them, as some farmers interviewed say: to find out about seminars, to search for information about an actor on the internet, to get appointments, to subscribe to an agricultural advice magazine or newspaper, to listen to radio programs on agriculture in order to better explore the themes that he brings out through research, to have access to distance or face-to-face training, to exchange interactively on networks or sites appropriate to the activity carried out, to be supervised by a system on a platform, or even to benefit from the experience of other producers. The whole thing is to evaluate the knowledge around him on the activities he practices and to capitalize on it. It should be noted that very few producers in our sample use this strategy. Of the nearly 14% who practice it in our sample, nearly 6% have higher education, nearly 4% have training in agriculture, nearly 3% have secondary education and nearly 1% have other levels of education.

II-5. The use of associative movements

the associative or consultation movement develops in rural areas through the various interdependent interactions that producers maintain with their environment. Associative movements are not new in rural Cameroon. They existed in various forms before the colonial era and were perpetuated through very distinct social structures (Tourte, 2005). During the colonial period, the first peasant grouping structures were the Indigenous Provident Societies (IPSS).

The IPSS aimed to combat hunger, but much more so to effectively ensure the supply of raw materials to industries, which is why their membership was mandatory (Guérin, 2008). With the emancipation of populations and decolonization movements, community movements evolved. However, it was with the economic crisis of the 1980s and the introduction of structural adjustment programs (SAPs) that we observed a profound reconfiguration of these movements in Cameroon, which were codified by laws in the early 1990s.

In our sample, several farmers are members of these community movements and consultation groups, namely 63% of producers. Their dynamism is increasingly visible through the weekly or monthly meetings of different strata, denominations, and social groups, and the projects in which they are involved as a community.

Indeed, these include organizations such as common initiative group (CIGs) and cooperatives. But also traditional associations of varying degrees of informality, originally based on religious, community, or cultural reasons, in which members organize themselves to improve their agricultural production.

Conclusion

The results presented in this study show that farmers' strategies for accessing information in rural areas are a matter of adapting to the transformation of their environment and of dynamism in preserving and building their

territory. Furthermore, these strategies revolve around two main axes: proximity, which in many respects requires punctuality in providing service, and accessibility, which refers to capitalizing on information and its use. The strategies for accessing agricultural advice developed by farmers in rural areas allow us to describe the local dynamics of the search for agricultural information and to understand the precariousness and dangers of informal advice from third parties (generalists), which are developing. This study presents agricultural advice as an environment where organizations, men and women, and structures coexist, attempting to implement agricultural and social development policy instruments on the ground. Because, alongside accredited agents, a large number of actors who can be described as generalists are much more sought after by farmers due to their proximity and the punctuality of disseminating agricultural information. To avoid being overwhelmed or resorting to fallback strategies, FAFs must be able to update themselves with the resources at their disposal to avoid bankruptcy, destruction, or loss of their environment. However, the supervision provided by formal agricultural advisory systems only benefits nearly 12% of the agricultural workers in our sample. This is why FAFs must find ways to access the information they need.

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